

A Mathematician

also known as “An Ethopoiia of a Mathematician”, “A Character Study as from a Presumptuous Mathematician, who Failed to Obtain a Bishopric Following the Fall of Constantinople”

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Entry tags: Christianity, Religious Group, Byzantine, Text, Medieval Christianity, Byzantine text, Orthodoxy

This short ethopoiia, or rhetorical personification, of a former teacher at the Patriarchal School of Hagia Sophia who was passed over for the see of Antioch in the years immediately after the Fourth Crusade, comes to us from the pen of the Byzantine bishop and literatus Nikolaos Mesarites, transmitted, along with the rest of his works, through Ambrosianus Graecus F93 and Ambrosianus Graecus F96. It is a critical corroborative source for some of the dimensions of Byzantine ecclesiastical politics in the earliest years of the Empire of Nicaea, as well as for the intrigue surrounding the appointment of an Orthodox Patriarch to the see of Antioch in 1205-1206. Effectively, during a succession crisis in the principality of Antioch, the Patriarchate had become vacant, and an Orthodox bishop, Symeon II, chosen from among the local Melkite community had been appointed by the Latin prince without reference to the exiled Ecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople. Evidently, the subject of the poem would have been endowed with the office by the Laskarid court, but the appointment of an Orthodox Patriarch in the person of Symeon II forced the emperor, in reluctant deference to the whims of a prince of the Outremer, to withdraw his candidate. The ethopoiia, therefore, is best read as a rhetorical device meant to salvage the reputation of those concerned by imputing to the candidate an unsuitable and preening fixation on astrology as a pretext for the retraction of the offered benefice. Likewise, in a context in which Nikolaos Mesarites and his brother Ioannes, in concert with those Byzantines who still remained in occupied Constantinople, were advocating for the appointment of another patriarch to the throne of the Latin-held capital, an action that relied on the case of Antioch to demonstrate precedent, it follows that it would have been in Mesarites' interests to discredit the subject of the ethopoiia. The tone of the piece, written in the voice of the failed candidate, is profoundly misanthropic, and fixated upon astrology as a means by which to deal with his own overweening ambition and moral turpitude, while also promising to assume a host of ailments in order to put a stop to the scorn of his associates. An aspect of the text which is not immediately obvious is the way in which it attests, albeit indirectly, to the diverse fields of knowledge in which a Byzantine bishop might be thought, however slanderously, to dabble, and bears out the critical place which astrology held in Byzantine understandings of their world even among the elite and those within the religious establishment.

Date Range: 1206 CE - 1207 CE

Region: Empire of Nicaea

Region tags: Asia Minor

The Empire of Nicaea 1204-1261

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Michael Angold, Nicholas Mesarites: His Life and Works (Liverpool, 2017), 297-305

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: N/A

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: N/A

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– No

↳ Cemetery
– No

↳ Temple
– No

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– No

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Bibliotheca Ambrosiana

↳ Specify

– Specify: Bibliotheca Ambrosiana

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Notes: I do not know the details of where in the institution it is kept.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Notes: I do not know the details of where in the institution it is kept.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The exact circumstances of the text's composition and its patron's relationship to the state is unclear, though it is possible to imagine that the patron was Patriarch Ioannes Kamateros who commissioned the author's Ekphrasis of the Church of the Holy Apostles.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is almost impossible to estimate how many people might have read or heard this composition.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– I don't know

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: A collection of Nicholas Mesarites' works.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: Ethopoiia, Character Study, Personification, Comedy

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: Progymnasmata such as Ethopoiia tend to contain a moralizing element, though not necessarily.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: N/A

Notes: It has none of these

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– I don't know

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is a sense of disdain for excessive intellectual pride as represented by the subjects devotion to astrology.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Field doesn't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: Byzantium might be considered either an Empire, or according to a Kaldellian formulation, a premodern nation-state.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: It is unclear in what circumstances the text was copied.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Primarily men received education in Byzantium.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: A Mathematician, Angold, Michael. "A Mathematician". In Nicholas Mesarites: His Life and Works, 297-305. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, 2017.